

Delphi consensus study – Round 4

We are very grateful to the 21 experts who participated to the three first rounds and welcome you to this important and final round. We think you have come to an agreement and that all your input has made it possible to come up with a sensible framework for a Mobility Management Program. During this round, you will therefore be asked to validate the overall framework. Unlike the other rounds, we have written a full report that summarizes all that has been discussed from the start. This report is the draft of the deliverable we will be able to use to communicate our results. We therefore need your feedback to improve it. We also need you to pronounce yourself about your satisfaction concerning the consensus that have been found.

This round includes 8 questions separated into 2 sections. We expect you will need 20-30 minutes to read the report. The entire round should therefore take you 30-45 minutes.

Comments:

Some participants had difficulties completing the questionnaire using Windows Explorer (e.i. not able to continue to next section). Their problem was solved by changing browser and using Chrome.

The term "client" can be interchanged with the term "patient". When caregivers are involved, the term "clients" refers to the person with health deficits and the caregiver.

1. Please provide your StudyID :

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Validation of changes brought to the "Treatment framework for mobility management during transport transition"

In this section, you are to validate the changes that have been brought to the treatment framework since round 3 taking into consideration your last comments and critics.

Framework deliverable

Please download the report using the following link (wetransfer link for a pdf file) :

<https://we.tl/UHsCD6WV5O>

Please read the report before answering the following questions:

2. Do you think that the program also needs to focus on changes in support networks ?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

3. If not, please explain your arguments.

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4. Do you agree that the final goal ought to be the autonomy of the entire network in managing future changes and not the autonomy of the client alone ?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

5. If not, please explain your arguments.

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6. Do you agree that the identification of the resources to implement the framework requires the implication of local and national authorities, policy makers, healthcare services, community services and social partners and thus cannot be clearly identified within this international consensus group ?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

7. If not, please explain your arguments.

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8. Do you agree that we should leave those commissioning the services to define further details on the modalities of their program ?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

9. If not, please explain your arguments.

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10. Do you think that the current framework is complete enough to give a good basis to work on at a national level ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not at all complete	<input type="radio"/>	As complete as it can get with a consensus study									

11. If not, please explain your arguments.

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12. How likely do you think such a program could be implemented in your country ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Not likely at all	<input type="radio"/>	Very likely									

Your previous comments during Round 3 (optional reading)

Question 1: Do you have any further critics or comments on the proposed treatment framework for managing mobility during transport transition ?

Wording

MOBILE8741 : I don't think that shortening the time until driving cessation is good. I would formulate that differently, like driving cessation happens when the person is ready for it.

MOBILE6211 : Some of the wording is difficult to follow (eg "Clients are confronted to positive experiences, such as the advantages in driving cessation and witnesses from peers"). I think the entry to the model via health professionals would only be relevant to a select few. We found most older driver participants in our programs self-referred and when interviewed GPs (although it is nominally their role) said they rarely get involved with driving cessation issues. This would vary in different contexts. VERY concerned that long term goal is to shorten time to driving cessation - premature cessation can be a big issue. Surely it should look at optimising timing of cessation rather than rushing people off the road before they need to be.

Lack of reality

MOBILE7125 : The stages in some sense seem to be 'imposed' on the driver/retiring driver. While the stages seem appropriate and plausible, the framework in some ways seems to lack some of the realities of the situation and the fact that people will not necessarily progress through the stages as effortlessly as the framework appears to suggest. Some people may never even get through stage 1 of 'consideration' because of awareness problems or denial of problems. I suppose in some ways the framework appears to reflect the 'ideal' pathway with extremely compliant drivers/retiring driver but may not reflect the reality.

MOBILE1394 : Stages may happen simultaneously: early involvement of caregiver, regardless of anosognosia/severe cognitive deficit: not clear who the dramatis personae may be, and may vary from setting to setting within a jurisdiction, and between jurisdictions.

MOBILE9567 : The model has sound theory base, but is very clinically applicable. The 4 stages are very clear. Stage 4 might never be achieved, as noted above. In addition, I think clients can become 'stuck' in any of the other stages as well. I have known many clients who don't move past stage one, and then the system takes over, removes the license and their transport is 'managed' for them. Some clients go on to work through the stages after this, and other don't and are always angry at the loss of driving and never properly grieve the loss of driving.

Not enough individualized

MOBILE8255 : I wonder about the timing for the development of goals and would suggest that this may come earlier. This is quite prescriptive and loses some of the very individual nature of this process. The setting of client centered goals earlier would ensure that this does not become a prescriptive process but rather one that truly meets the individuals' needs.

Cognitive decline

MOBILE3618 : I think stage 2 (Acceptance) needs to talk briefly also about clients with lack of insight due to cognitive decline.

MOBILE3776 : I believe all this works for normal aging. It does not work for people who have dementia. The lack of insight is not there unless this is done in the very very early stages.

Primary outcome

MOBILE7932 : Primary outcome should include mobility not just improving mental well-being.

Other

MOBILE6893 : I really like the multidisciplinary team model depicted. I tried to have a similar group program offered within a community health setting. Two problems - firstly my manager said it was a conflict of interest as the driving is provided through my private practice, not through the health centre. Secondly, potential clients were reluctant to become involved if participation meant that they may be reported to our Roads Authority as not being physically or cognitively able to drive and require testing, with the possibility of losing their licence. Because of the lack of transport alternatives, we are really constrained in supporting and assisting clients in transition to retaining any degree of independence without huge financial imposts such as the use of taxis. Even if people are on a care package, the large distances involved in my area for people to access shops and social or health services means that maybe only one trip per week or fortnight could be funded.

Agreement

MOBILE4380 : The framework appears to be all inclusive and well thought out.

Question 2 : Do you have any further critics or comments on the above table (domains of change) ?

Reality - "ideal process"

MOBILE7125 : I think again that it reflects an 'ideal' type process. I don't think that the process is a clean-cut as the table suggests. I think behaviour change and changing lifelong habits and routines is extremely difficult and some of the suggested alternatives may not be acceptable to the retiring driver. I would also caution against the tendency in the table that seem to expect 'new learning' will occur - for example if a person is being advised to cease or retire from driving because they have dementia and it is impairing their cognitive ability to drive, then expecting behavioural changes such as learning to use new technology may be unrealistic for these people, also changing routines and habits and learning new tasks may be very compromised. I think this table reflects an approach that may work with "WELL" older people to begin planning for driver retirement into their future, but the reality is that most people do not engage with this and it is only when driving becomes problematic that driving gets addressed - and by that time it may be too late for some to engage in proactively in behaviour change.

MOBILE8255 : I am still really unsure of how this is relevant. I have raised my concerns about this previously. This is forcing a very unique experience into boxes into which a persons goal may not fit. For example, the person who would like to gain confidence in using alternate transport. I believe that although there is some commonality to the practical and psychological aspects - there is a risk of developing a matrix like this which will see an intervention developed that is driven by tick boxes rather than an individual's need. I believe this (and the next question) may have been the section in the previous survey that I just stopped completing because I felt that I could not endorse it.

Changes taken into account

MOBILE4380 : In my practice, the clients who still have the ability to adjust memory etc, have already done so and worked through this process themselves. The areas of Extrapersonal an Transport are usually arranged by family and carers not the client. As I work in a rural area relocation is quite limited and usually is arranged by the family and the client is relocated to be near family and supports.

MOBILE6893 : As someone who has done formal grief counselling training, I do not like the use of the term "overcome the notion of loss and grief." That term diminishes the value of all the roles noted in the model, as well as the attachments of the clients to these roles and activities. There have been instances of clients threatening or performing self-harm after failing the test, so the importance of driving cannot be underestimated. Caregivers often do not drive - especially if they are female. Gophers are only of value if the client has the physical and cognitive skills to operate them, or they live within a town boundary. Community services are scarce - there is a 10 week waiting list for a home assessment for an OT in our community, and similar for many other services. Government funding is reduced/reviewed/restructured often threatening continuity with the provision of services that would assist the client to work through the above stages.

MOBILE6211 : I find some of these to be overlapping. I still find relocation not very separate from the occupation/transport; Also not very clear on cognitive processes as a domain.

MOBILE9567 : This is an excellent description. It does require good executive functions and flexibility of thought to reason through these levels and descriptors and put into practice. I am working with another OT and she is trying to bring about behaviour change with older people in activity self-pacing. And what we are finding (and it might be the same with older people using this transport change approach), is that some older people have very concrete thought, and it can be challenging to work with these clients and facilitate them to engage in these new ways of thinking and accept these new patterns of living.

MOBILE3499 : Not sure what you mean by 'gopher'. Again some of the behavioural changes have significant resource implications. How this model works for people who have resource issues and less choice to make behavioural changes.

More general

MOBILE6022 : Providing examples that are meaningful to a large proportion of the intended

audience is extremely difficult and failure to do so may limit its perceived relevance to the user i.e. 'taking the bus and train to visit gynaecologist'. Useful examples that are culturally/gender/class neutral should be considered.

Others

MOBILE7932 : I wonder about using 'affective functioning' or something to that effect as opposed to 'emotional attachments.' As well under the description for cognitive process 'learning to manage within current capabilities' - what about also learning to manage in advance of changes - again, the anticipatory approach is also key with regard to 'anticipating' potential changes ahead and putting adaptations and accommodations in place. Below, do not understand the question related Figure 3 and am inserting this comment here, as there is no spot to put that in relation to question (re: "Do you find relevant to consider changes as a continuous process taking place throughout the four stages of Mobility Management Programs ? ") Not sure how to answer this question in terms of what I find relevant as I'm not sure what is being asked.

MOBILE1394 : Misses out on pleasure/locus of control aspect of driving

Question 3 : Do you agree with our suggestions and if you do not, could you develop why and make further suggestions (underlying theoretical models)?

Reality :

MOBILE7125 : It is important to link in the theory into the model development. However, a problem with this is that it often reflects an 'ideal' and sometimes unrealistic view and may not reflect the reality. The changes do seem appropriate and enhance the model. But the model does seem to 'expect' change to occur and in reality people do not fit neatly into these types of models.

MOBILE6893 : As a clinician, I have always found it difficult to work using the principles or processes systematically from one model. As someone working in an understaffed and under-resourced setting, I have had to juggle the concepts from a number of approaches. Hence, at this stage, I cannot confidently state that I practise in accordance with any model.

MOBILE5446 : Generally I do agree with the suggestions - however, it is important to keep in mind that the context and environment greatly determine whether the suggestions are relevant and can be implemented or not. For example, there needs to be a focus on advocating for adequate time and resources to apply these strategies across health care domains.

Comprehension issues:

Again, I'm not sure I understand the question that goes along with this scale.

Other :

MOBILE1394 : Not clear that the process is quite so amenable to be captured in these theoretical terms: more qualitative research needed among compromised drivers

MOBILE3776 : I believe that a client and caregiver may agree with a health professional, but then not activate this in reality. Clients often comment that the healthcare provider does not know what he/she is talking about.

MOBILE6211 : I am not familiar with some of the models/theories you discuss and therefore can't agree or disagree.

Agreement

MOBILE4380 : I am happy with the suggestions

MOBILE3032 : yes

MOBILE7564 : Yes

MOBILE5118 : I agree

MOBILE9567 : These suggestions sound very reasonable. i am joing in at stage 3, so I havent been involved in developing the selection of models and intervention approach. I am not familiar with Behvaiour Change Technique Taxonomy and will look this up on the web address given after completing the round. .

MOBILE3499 : yes

MOBILE8741 : yes

General appreciation of the consensus search process

13. To what extent are you satisfied about that consensus that was found through this study ?

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very unsatisfied	<input type="radio"/>	Totally satisfied									

14. Considering what we should achieve with this round, do you see the need for an extra round after this one ?

Mark only one oval.

Yes
 No

15. Do you have any further critics or comments ?

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End of Round 4

You have answered the last question. You will be invited for the next round on February 15th. To validate your answers, press the submit button on this page.

